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Assessing Ecological Connectivity of Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve, Ghana, Based on Landcover Types.

Bewertung der ökologischen Vernetzung des Biosphärenreservats Bosomtwe-See, Ghana, anhand von Landbedeckungstypen

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Streszczenie

Ocena łączności ekologicznej Rezerwatu Biosfery Jeziora Bosomtwe w Ghanie na podstawie typów pokrycia terenu

Łączność ekologiczna ma kluczowe znaczenie dla zachowania różnorodności biologicznej i utrzymania procesów ekosystemowych. Niniejsze badanie ocenia łączność ekologiczną rezerwatu biosfery Lake Bosomtwe w Ghanie przy użyciu danych dotyczących pokrycia terenu i algorytmu Omniscape (McRae i in., 2006) do modelowania ruchu w biosferze. Poprzez przypisanie wartości oporu i wagi źródła do różnych typów pokrycia terenu, łączność krajobrazu jest reprezentowana jako prądy elektryczne.

Badania generują trzy kluczowe wyniki poprzez analizę danych rastrowych pokrycia terenu w rozdzielczości 20 metrów w całej Afryce, w oparciu o roczne obserwacje Sentinel-2A od grudnia 2015 r. do grudnia 2016 r. (Europejska Agencja Kosmiczna [ESA], 2016). Wyniki te obejmują skumulowany przepływ prądu, potencjał przepływu i znormalizowany przepływ prądu. Niniejsze badanie ma na celu: 1) identyfikację wzorców przepływu w biosferze, 2) ocenę wpływu topografii na wzorce przepływu oraz 3) identyfikację priorytetowych obszarów ochrony i potencjalnych korytarzy przemieszczania się.

Wyniki wskazują, że pokrycie drzewami stanowi znaczną część skumulowanego obecnego przepływu (81,88%) i potencjału przepływu (71,26%), podkreślając jego znaczenie w utrzymaniu łączności. Grunty uprawne również odgrywają dominującą rolę w przepływie ekologicznym, podczas gdy obszary zabudowane i nieosłonięte wykazują wysoki opór dla przepływu. Analiza znormalizowanego bieżącego przepływu pokazuje, że 13,69% krajobrazu doświadcza przepływu utrudnionego, 7,35% ma przepływ rozproszony, a 18,14% wykazuje przepływ skanalizowany, przy czym żaden obszar nie wykazuje przepływu zintensyfikowanego.

Istnieje silna dodatnia korelacja ($r = 0,91$) między potencjałem przepływu a skumulowanym bieżącym przepływem, potwierdzająca wpływ elementów krajobrazu na łączność ekologiczną. Dodatkowo korelacja Pearsona ($r = 0,76$) między potencjałem przepływu a znormalizowanym przepływem prądu wskazuje na złożoną nieliniową zależność. Analiza korytarzy ujawnia, że 17,20% badanego krajobrazu obejmuje istotne korytarze, które są

pofragmentowane na 2526 płatów, co podkreśla pilną potrzebę działań ochronnych. Co więcej, analiza topograficzna wskazuje na strome zbocza (średnie nachylenie: $64,10^\circ$), które wpływają na wzorce ruchu, z większymi skumulowanymi prądami występującymi na niezakłóconych obszarach.

Badanie zaleca usuwanie barier, ochronę korytarzy, wdrażanie zrównoważonych praktyk użytkowania gruntów i angażowanie społeczności w celu zwiększenia łączności ekologicznej i ochrony biosfery.

Słowa kluczowe: Łączność ekologiczna, Ochrona różnorodności biologicznej, Analiza korytarzy, Algorytm Omniscape, Topografia

Abstract

Assessing Ecological Connectivity of Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve, Ghana based on Landcover Types

Ecological connectivity is crucial for conserving biodiversity and maintaining ecosystem processes. This study assesses the ecological connectivity of the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve in Ghana using land cover data and the Omniscape algorithm (McRae et al., 2006) to model movement within the biosphere. By assigning resistance and source weight values to various land cover types, landscape connectivity is represented as electrical currents.

The research generates three key outputs by analyzing land cover raster data at a 20-meter resolution across Africa, based on one year of Sentinel-2A observations from December 2015 to December 2016 (European Space Agency [ESA], 2016). These outputs include cumulative current flow, flow potential, and normalized current flow. This study aims to: 1) identify flow patterns within the biosphere, 2) assess the impact of topography on flow patterns, and 3) identify priority conservation areas and potential movement corridors.

The results indicate that tree cover accounts for a significant portion of cumulative current flow (81.88%) and flow potential (71.26%), underscoring its importance in maintaining connectivity. Cropland also plays a dominant role in ecological flow, while built-up and bare areas exhibit high resistance to flow. The analysis of normalized current flow shows that 13.69% of the landscape experiences impeded flow, 7.35% has diffuse flow, and 18.14% exhibits channelized flow, with no areas displaying intensified flow.

A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.91$) exists between flow potential and cumulative current flow, validating the influence of landscape elements on ecological connectivity. Additionally, Pearson correlation ($r = 0.76$) between flow potential and normalized current flow indicates a complex non-linear relationship. Corridor analysis reveals that 17.20% of the study landscape comprises essential corridors, which are fragmented into 2,526 patches, highlighting the urgent need for conservation efforts. Furthermore, topographic analysis shows steep slopes (average inclination: 64.10°) that influence movement patterns, with greater cumulative currents found in undisturbed areas.

The study recommends removing barriers, protecting channelized corridors, implementing sustainable land-use practices, and engaging communities to enhance ecological connectivity and conservation within the biosphere.

Key words: Ecological connectivity, Biodiversity conservation, Corridor analysis, Omniscape algorithm, Topography

Zusammenfassung

Bewertung der ökologischen Vernetzung des Biosphärenreservats Bosomtwe-See, Ghana, anhand von Landbedeckungstypen

Die ökologische Vernetzung ist entscheidend für die Erhaltung der biologischen Vielfalt und die Aufrechterhaltung von Ökosystemprozessen. In dieser Studie wird die ökologische Konnektivität des Biosphärenreservats Bosomtwe-See in Ghana anhand von Landbedeckungsdaten und dem Omniscape-Algorithmus (McRae et al., 2006) zur Modellierung von Bewegungen innerhalb der Biosphäre bewertet. Durch die Zuweisung von Widerstands- und Quellengewichtswerten zu verschiedenen Landbedeckungstypen wird die Landschaftskonnektivität als elektrische Ströme dargestellt.

Durch die Analyse von Landbedeckungsrasterdaten mit einer Auflösung von 20 Metern in ganz Afrika, die auf einjährigen Sentinel-2A-Beobachtungen von Dezember 2015 bis Dezember 2016 basieren (Europäische Weltraumorganisation [ESA], 2016), werden drei wichtige Ergebnisse erzielt. Diese Ergebnisse umfassen den kumulativen Stromfluss, das Strompotenzial und den normalisierten Stromfluss. Ziel dieser Studie ist es: 1) Strömungsmuster innerhalb der Biosphäre zu identifizieren, 2) die Auswirkungen der Topografie auf die Strömungsmuster zu bewerten und 3) prioritäre Schutzgebiete und potenzielle Bewegungskorridore zu identifizieren.

Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass die Baumbedeckung einen bedeutenden Teil des kumulativen aktuellen Flusses (81,88 %) und des Flusspotenzials (71,26 %) ausmacht, was ihre Bedeutung für die Aufrechterhaltung des Verbunds unterstreicht. Ackerland spielt ebenfalls eine dominante Rolle beim ökologischen Fluss, während bebaute und kahle Flächen einen hohen Widerstand gegen den Fluss aufweisen. Die Analyse der normalisierten Strömung zeigt, dass 13,69 % der Landschaft eine behinderte Strömung, 7,35 % eine diffuse Strömung und 18,14 % eine kanalisierte Strömung aufweisen, wobei keine Gebiete eine verstärkte Strömung aufweisen.

Es besteht eine starke positive Korrelation ($r = 0,91$) zwischen dem Durchflusspotenzial und dem kumulativen aktuellen Durchfluss, was den Einfluss von Landschaftselementen auf die ökologische Vernetzung bestätigt. Darüber hinaus deutet die Pearson-Korrelation ($r = 0,76$)

zwischen dem Durchflusspotenzial und dem normalisierten aktuellen Durchfluss auf eine komplexe nicht-lineare Beziehung hin. Die Korridoranalyse zeigt, dass 17,20 % der untersuchten Landschaft aus wichtigen Korridoren bestehen, die in 2.526 Flecken fragmentiert sind, was die dringende Notwendigkeit von Schutzmaßnahmen verdeutlicht. Darüber hinaus zeigt die topografische Analyse steile Hänge (durchschnittliche Neigung: $64,10^\circ$), die die Bewegungsmuster beeinflussen, wobei in ungestörten Gebieten größere kumulative Strömungen festgestellt wurden.

Die Studie empfiehlt die Beseitigung von Hindernissen, den Schutz von kanalisiertem Korridoren, die Umsetzung nachhaltiger Landnutzungspraktiken und die Einbeziehung von Gemeinden, um die ökologische Vernetzung und den Schutz innerhalb der Biosphäre zu verbessern.

Schlüsselbegriffe: Ökologischer Verbund, Erhaltung der biologischen Vielfalt, Korridoranalyse, Omniscape-Algorithmus, Topographie

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CHAPTER ONE

1. Introduction

Connectivity emerged as a key concept in landscape ecology in the 1990s and was originally defined as “the degree to which the landscape facilitates or impedes movement among resource patches” (Taylor et al., 1993). It is essential for maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem health. Ensuring effective ecological connectivity is one way to mitigate the negative impacts of habitat fragmentation and biodiversity loss. The destruction of landscape connectivity has severe consequences for biodiversity conservation (Hanski, 2005).

Human activities such as land conversion for agriculture, residential, and commercial uses, as well as the construction of roads, railways, and transmission lines, significantly modify ecosystems (Kennedy et al., 2019). The direct impact of urbanization and other anthropogenic factors is the isolation and fragmentation of habitats, leading to increased disturbance, habitat degradation, and reduced genetic diversity (Tabor et al., 2019). In fragmented landscapes, organisms survive in habitat patches linked by dispersal, but habitat loss and fragmentation remain major threats to biodiversity (Tilman et al., 2017). The segmentation of natural landscapes has resulted in species, including mammals, moving significantly less than they once did, restricting their ability to migrate, disperse, mate, feed, and thrive, ultimately increasing the risk of extinction (Tabor et al., 2019). Fragmentation triggers a chain reaction of ecological dysfunction, including food web breakdowns, nutrient cycle disruptions, and species extinctions (Fahrig, 1997).

Research on ecological connectivity in Ghana has been ongoing for several years, with significant studies emerging in the early 2000s (Owubah et al., 2001). More recent studies (R. Asare et al., 2014) have explored the role of cocoa agroforestry in enhancing forest connectivity in fragmented landscapes. However, increasing urbanization and other anthropogenic activities have significantly impacted ecological connectivity in Ghana’s reserves (Danso et al., 2021).

With the acceleration of these activities, many reserves in Ghana are losing their support systems for species survival (Atanga et al., 2024), posing a severe threat to biodiversity conservation. Habitat degradation has placed several species in Ghana at critical risk of extinction, and this decline in biodiversity is expected to rise (Wu et al., 2019). Furthermore, the loss of connectivity threatens the sustainability of ecosystem services that serve fringing

communities, including freshwater availability, soil fertility, and climate regulation (Keesstra et al., 2018).

Land cover datasets are commonly used to parameterize resistance for connectivity modeling (Landau et al., 2021). Different land cover types support various habitats and influence ecological processes crucial for maintaining healthy ecosystems. Fragmentation within land cover types creates barriers that lead to population declines and reduced genetic diversity (Wang & Cheng, 2022). Assessing ecological connectivity is essential for biodiversity conservation planning, ensuring species survival, and maintaining continuous gene flow (McGuire et al., 2016).

Maintaining ecological connectivity is also important for the sustainability of the agroforestry systems, which provide critical corridors for biodiversity in human-altered landscapes. Studies have shown that tree cover in agricultural mosaics can facilitate species movement and maintain genetic flow between isolated populations (Perfecto & Vandermeer, 2010).

Lake Bosomtwe, a unique natural landmark in Ghana, plays a significant role in conservation (A. Asare et al., 2021). Its rich biodiversity makes it a critical ecological area. However, challenges such as carrying capacity limitations, overuse of fish resources, and excessive extraction of forest stock have led to overexploitation and ecosystem degradation. These factors threaten the ecological integrity of the reserve (Rottig et al., 2024). The resulting fragmentation of the biosphere habitat impacts gene flow and species movement, negatively affecting biodiversity conservation efforts.

Given its importance for biodiversity conservation, the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve offers a special opportunity to assess ecological connectivity and plan efficient conservation strategies. The likelihood of Habitat fragmentation within the biosphere, when assessed for its ecological connectivity, would not only serve the biosphere but could serve as a model for similar landscapes in Ghana and could also serve as a model for designing conservation plans.

A delicate balance of biodiversity and people's livelihood is challenging, yet finding sustainable solutions could provide valuable lessons to other regions where the same challenges are being realized (Smith et al., 2023)

1.1 Problem Statement

The fragmentation of habitats and the loss of connectivity in Ghana's biosphere reserves due to activities like urban development and changes in land use have significantly impacted efforts to protect biodiversity in the region. This fragmentation has led to isolation among species and a decline in diversity while also increasing the risk of extinction for animals and plants. Despite research efforts focusing on connectivity in Ghana's wildlife areas, the rapid expansion of activities is outpacing conservation initiatives. This leads to habitat destruction and degradation along with the loss of support systems for species survival, posing a threat to the long-term balance of ecosystems.

1.2 Objective

This study aims to assess ecological connectivity in the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve using pre-classified land cover raster data to identify conservation priority areas, the impact of topography on flow patterns, and the distribution of flow patterns (flow potential, cumulative current flow, normalized current flow) across the biosphere reserve. The research considers the structural elements of the landscape by identifying barriers and corridors that facilitate or impede ecological connectivity within the reserve.

Specific Objectives:

1. To investigate the ecological connectivity of various land cover types within the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve. This examines how different land cover types facilitate or hinder connectivity and further analyzes the relationship between flow dynamics and corridors.
2. To evaluate ecological connectivity in a varied landscape while considering the influence of topography. This analyzes how elevation, slope, and aspect affect connectivity.
3. To identify priority conservation areas within the biosphere reserve that need to be conserved and protected. This integrates connectivity and topography to pinpoint critical areas.

This study prioritizes structural connectivity without accounting for the varying habitat needs of different species or predicting future climate changes. The outcomes of this research aim to support conservation planning and management strategies in the Biosphere Reserve, ultimately enhancing ecological integrity and preserving biodiversity.

CHAPTER TWO

2. Literature Review

Ecological connectivity refers to the capacity of a landscape to support effective pathways for species movement, facilitated by interconnected habitat patches, which are essential for sustaining ecological processes such as pollination, nutrient cycling, and decomposition (Tabor et al., 2019). This concept emerged in landscape ecology in the 1990s and focuses on how landscapes, whether natural, semi-natural, or human-modified, support ecological processes (Taylor et al., 1993; McRae et al., 2016). Ecological connectivity is vital for species' adaptation to environmental changes, helping buffer disruptions such as climate change and habitat fragmentation (Tabor et al., 2019).

Earlier, the focus was primarily on large mammals and how habitat fragmentation affects their migration patterns (Forman et al., 1986). Over time, the scope of connectivity research expanded to encompass the effects of urbanization and human activities on habitat fragmentation and the establishment of habitat corridors (Hilty et al., 2012). This research underlines the importance of connectivity in conserving and restoring biodiversity and ecosystem services (Hilty et al., 2012; Crooks et al., 2006).

Connectivity as a concept gained traction in the early 1990s, primarily concerning how landscapes either facilitate or impede species movement between habitat patches (Taylor et al., 1993). The understanding of connectivity evolved as researchers recognized the importance of both the structural elements of landscapes and the ecological processes they support. The importance of habitat corridors for gene flow and wildlife movement became clearer, especially in light of increasing anthropogenic threats to ecosystems (Bennett, 2003; Crooks et al., 2006).

Modeling connectivity has been a significant focus of ecological research, driven in part by the extinction risks of species due to climate change and habitat fragmentation (Belote et al., 2022). The recognition of these challenges led to the development of different modeling approaches that quantify the impact of habitat loss, fragmentation, and human disturbances on connectivity (Kennedy et al., 2019; Zeller et al., 2024).

Various methodologies have been developed to model connectivity, each with its strengths and limitations. These include the least-cost approach, resistant kernels, circuit theory, and

species-specific models (Tabor et al., 2019). The least-cost approach, for example, uses resistance surfaces to estimate movement paths, while the resistant kernels method measures flow at multiple scales (Zeller et al., 2024). One notable development in connectivity modeling is the use of circuit theory (McRae et al., 2006), which treats the landscape as a network of resources and resistors, with the omniscap algorithm enhancing connectivity estimations in landscapes lacking clear core areas. The omniscap approach, building on earlier innovations in circuit theory (McRae et al., 2006; McRae et al., 2008), has been effective in estimating flow patterns and spatial connectivity (Shah & McRae, 2008; Anantharaman et al., 2020).

Recent research has also explored species-agnostic models, which offer a generalized view of connectivity but may not capture species-specific movement behavior (Theobald et al., 2012; Walker et al., 1997). These models emphasize the role of structural connectivity, geodiversity, and climate modeling in shaping ecological movement across landscapes (McRae et al., 2016).

Landscape connectivity models have been applied in a variety of contexts, such as wildlife corridors and water security assessments (DeFries et al., 2023; Dohee Kim et al., 2020). The importance of connectivity in mitigating the impacts of habitat fragmentation is evident in studies that use land cover maps to estimate corridors for improving ecological linkages (Kim et al., 2020). Additionally, Zeller et al. (2024) employed resistant kernels to assess connectivity across different landscape scales, providing insights into habitat corridors and connectivity restoration strategies.

Substantial progress has been made in other parts of the world, particularly in countries like the USA and Canada, but the application of ecological connectivity strategies in Ghana remains limited. In Ghana, there has been little to no effort in identifying barriers to connectivity or recognizing areas that could facilitate the movement of organisms. This highlights the need for further research and policy development to incorporate connectivity into land management and biodiversity conservation strategies in the Lake Bosomtwe biosphere reserve.

CHAPTER THREE

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Study Area

Lake Bosomtwe is the only natural lake in Ghana with an exceptional history of origin, some authors attribute it to a caldera formation when the top of a volcano blew off (Boateng et al., 2023) while other authors describe the natural lake as a result of an impact crater from a meteorite impact 1.07 million years ago. It is a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, the oldest and deepest natural lake in West Africa. Lake Bosomtwe is one of the six meteoritic lakes in the world and was nominated in 2016 as a major tourist site in Ghana (UNESCO,2016). The reserve serves as a habitat for various fauna and flora species while supporting Ghana's economy through tourism and microeconomic activities that benefit surrounding communities (Avel, 2023). The lake is treated as sacred and has a cultural significance (Amu-Mensah et al.,2017). It comprises forest, wetland, and mountain ecosystems. The reserve is fringed by 24 communities, with about 50,000 people who live from fishing and subsistence farming (Asare et al., 2021).

The Lake Bosomtwe Reserve is situated in the Bosomtwe District of Ghana latitude 6° 30 N and longitude 1° 25 W (UNESCO, 2016). The reserve is found within Bosomtwe, Bosome Freho, and Bekwai municipalities. It has a climate of a wet semi-equatorial belt in Ghana characterized by high temperatures and substantial annual rainfall, fostering rich biodiversity and rich vegetation. The Biosphere Reserve comprises a surface of almost 225,490 ha consisting of a core area of 43,878 ha, a Buffer zone of 73,400 ha, and a Transition zone of 108,212 ha (Rottig et al.,2024).

Figure 1. Map of the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve showing the lake, buffer zone (4.8km), transition zone (7.2km), settlements, and roads

3.2 Overview

Omniscape is used to model the movement of species within a landscape, defining connectivity as the degree to which different land cover types sustain ecological connectivity (McRae et al., 2016). In this analysis, the input data used to simulate the randomized movement of species within the landscape consists of the land cover types within the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve.

Omniscape is an advancement of the Circuitscape algorithm, simulating ecological connectivity by representing sources, destinations, and species movement intensity as electric currents, while treating the landscape surface as resistance (Shah et al., 2015; McRae et al., 2008). The algorithm requires two key inputs; a source layer which represents areas within the landscape that may serve as species habitats, illustrated by pixels corresponding to different land cover types. and resistance layer representing landscape elements that hinder species movement, with pixels indicating varying resistance levels (Goh, 2024).

Omniscape employs a moving window approach to quantify connectivity between a target grid cell and all surrounding grid cells within a set distance. This process is repeated

iteratively across the entire landscape (Thorne et al., 2020). The algorithm produces three key outputs that illustrate the spatial distribution of ecological connectivity:

Cumulative Current Flow which represents the summed likelihood of species movement, identifying areas with high and low movement potential.

Flow Potential depicting movement across the landscape without resistance, illustrating total potential movement in the absence of barriers.

Normalized Current Flow as a results of normalizing the cumulative current flow over the flow potential to assess the impact of the landscape on movement (McRae, Beier, & Shah, 2008).

The normalized current flow map classifies landscape areas based on connectivity impact.

Areas with values less than one indicate impeded flow, while those with values greater than one signify channelized flow (Landau et al., 2021). Additional classifications include

intensified and diffuse flow zones (McRae et al., 2016). Channelized flow areas are particularly critical for conservation efforts, as they serve as essential corridors for ecological connectivity.

3.2.1 The Omniscape algorithm

The omniscape algorithm identifies the central pixel, given that its source strength exceeds 0.

A moving window evaluates the centre pixel's positivity; if positive, it adjusts the resistance and source raster to the window's boundaries. This procedure continually assesses other pixels with strengths above 0 while progressing, aiming to determine potential movement targets. The identified pixels receive currents proportional to the source strength of the central pixel, which is divided by the source strengths of the other identified pixels. The currents from all target pixels across every possible resistance path are then aggregated. This cycle repeats for all pixels with a source strength greater than 0, leading to the total cumulative current flow (Shah, McRae, & Beier, 2015).

Figure 2. Illustration of a moving window iteration in the Omniscape algorithm. Source: McRae, B. (2016). [<https://docs.circuitscape.org/Omniscape.jl/latest/algorithm/>].

3.3 Data

This study utilizes a high-resolution land cover map at 20m resolution over Africa, based on one year of Sentinel-2A observations from December 2015 to December 2016 by the European Space Agency (ESA). This data was selected because it was the only available dataset classified by experts within my study area. The Sentinel-2 prototype land cover raster map of Africa for 2016 includes 10 generic classes that describe the land surface at 20m, consisting of: tree cover, shrub cover, grassland, built-up areas, cropland, bare areas, open

water, sparse vegetation, and aquatic or regularly flooded vegetation (European Space Agency [ESA], 2016).

To generate an input raster for this research, we utilize the study area, including the buffer and transition zone, to clip the S2 prototype LC 20m. This process involves assigning source and resistance values to each of the 10 classes. The source values are obtained from the landcover data by analyzing the raster data pixels. Resistance values indicate how well the landscape elements can connect to support ecological processes. The resistance of the Lake is assumed to be missing because the research focuses on the accessible zones of the Lake Bosomtwe biosphere reserve. Other resistance values are modeled based on landcover types, with certain types exhibiting lower resistance due to their potential for ecological connectivity, while others have higher resistance values.

Figure 3. Land cover types of the study area, showing the percentage distribution of land cover types.

Figure 4. Classified land cover map of the study area

3.3.1 Modeling Input Data

The input data show landscape elements as resistance surfaces, focusing on land cover types within the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve. Low resistance values have been assigned to land cover types that are easy to cross when moving, while high values have been given to those land covers impeding movement. The Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve comprises forest, mountain, and wetland ecosystems. Tree and shrub cover are key components of the forest ecosystem. These land cover types represent continuous habitats considered natural corridors for improving gene flow and ecological connectivity (Sahraoui et al., 2017). The built-up and cropland areas, however, are considered to act as a barrier to ecological connectivity.

Natural areas were given higher source weight scores due to their facilitation of movement and, thus, potentially greater ecological flow. The resistance and source weight files were then used in the analysis of ecological connectivity within the study area. The resistance file is derived from assigning resistance values to the landcover raster data of the study area (Landau et al., 2021).

Tree cover, shrub cover, grassland, and vegetative aquatic are considered natural, and likely modified areas are cropland, built-up areas, and bare areas. A resistance value of 1 indicates low or no resistance (high connectivity), while a value of 1000 reflects complete immobility (low connectivity). Natural areas are given low resistance values, while human-modified areas are assigned high resistance values (McRae et al., 2016). The resistance values assigned to each land cover type are presented in Table 1. In the light of connectivity principles, natural areas serve as those with optimal conditions for species movement and survival (McRae et al., 2016). These areas are thereby of special importance in conservation planning as they enhance connectivity more strongly than artificial or human-modified landscape conditions.

Furthermore, the analysis was conducted using Python and Julia, utilizing their computing capabilities to simulate ecological connectivity. Data pre-treatment, raster management, statistical analysis, and visualizations were carried out with Python (Harris et al., 2020; Jordahl et al., 2018), while Julia, specifically the Omniscape.jl package, was employed to perform the connectivity simulations (Bezanson et al., 2017; McRae et al., 2016). Both programming languages complemented each other by facilitating the efficient processing of high-resolution spatial data and generating connectivity maps and several graphs for the study.

In addition, the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was used in this study to incorporate topographic factors into the ecological connectivity modeling. The DEM was in a spatial resolution of 30m and the EPSG:4326 coordinate system. Processed in Python, the DEM provided elevation and slope data to calibrate resistance values so that landscape gradients can be adequately represented in ecological connectivity modeling

Table 1. Resistance values assigned to different land cover types with the open water completely missing

Landcover Types	Resistance
Tree Cover	1
Grassland	30
Shrub Cover	1
Crop Land	300
Bare Area	100
Built up	1000
Vegetation aquatic	40

CHAPTER FOUR

4. Results

Omniscape analysis created three output maps: cumulative current flow, normalized current flow, and flow potential to represent the spatial pattern of ecological connectivity within the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve. The maps provide details about potential movement pathways with greater, hindered, or spreading flow throughout the landscape, portraying areas with accelerated, hindered, or fragmented flow (Shah & McRae, 2018).

4.1 Normalized Current Flow

The spatial pattern of normalized cumulative current flow over the study area shows impeded, diffuse, channelized, and intensified with Lake acting as a complete barrier to flow, and this exhibits significant heterogeneity over the landscape.

The impeded flow of 13.69% is characterized by areas where flow of current is hindered, perhaps by land, vegetation, or other physical barriers. The relatively high rate of impeded flow suggests the presence of major man-made barriers.

Diffuse flow of regions with 7.35% of the study area are regions of low-density, wide current movement.

The limited extent of the diffuse flow region shows that there is no concentration of flow into single channels but broadly spread throughout the landscape, covering few areas.

As shown in Figure 5, Channelized flow is the most dominant flow category; 18.14% of the study area shows the existence of well-defined routes or channels along which current movement is concentrated, perhaps characteristic of connectivity

Surprisingly, none of the locations within the study area experienced intensified flow. This absence is suggestive of a deficiency of highly focused flow pathways, possibly because of the non-existence of significant infrastructure that aims to focus flow.

Figure 5. Normalized current flow of the study area

Figure 6. Normalized current flow categories of the study area

4.2 Cumulative Current Flow

The analysis indicates that Tree Cover contributes the largest percentage of the total summed current, contributing approximately 81.88%. This indicates that tree-covered areas have a dominant effect on the flow of current, possibly due to their large spatial extent or resistance characteristics. Crop Land is the second contributor, contributing 14.84% of the total summed current.

Figure 7. Cumulative current flow of the study area

This indicates a high contribution, which could be due to agricultural activities and associated land use patterns. Shrub Cover accounts for 2.18% of the total current, representing a considerably small but meaningful contribution to the overall distribution. All the rest of the land cover classes, such as Grassland, Bare Area, Built-up areas, and Vegetative Aquatic, all account for less than 1% of the total current. Precisely, Grassland accounts for 0.02%, Bare Area for 0.18%, Built-up for 0.87%, and Vegetative Aquatic for 0.03%.

These results, as shown in *figure 8*, highlight the dominant influence of tree cover on cumulative current and highlight the relatively lesser roles played by other land covers. This insight is useful for understanding landscape dynamics and informing land management.

Figure 8. Cumulative current flow distribution of the landcover types

4.3 Flow Potential

The pie chart, as shown in *figure 9*, indicates that most of the flow potential occurs in Tree Cover-dominant areas, which is 71.26% of the overall flow potential. The large percentage implies that tree-covered land has a substantial contribution to enhancing or influencing flow potential in the landscape. Crop Land is the second most dominant land cover type, with a contribution of 23.21% to the overall flow potential. This indicates that agricultural lands play an important role in affecting flow potential, probably because of changed surface properties concerning cultivation activities.

Figure 9. Flow potential distribution of the landcover types

Figure 10. Flow potential of the study area

Shrub Cover with a percentage of 2.99% indicates a moderate impact on flow potential. Urban with 2.06% depicts the influence of impervious surfaces on flow characteristics. The other land covers, including Bare Area (0.37%), Vegetative Aquatic (0.08%), and Grassland (0.03%), indicate minimal influence on the distribution of flow potential. Overall, the findings point to the dominance of vegetated cover, particularly tree cover and agricultural land, in contributing to the cumulative flow potential of the landscape.

4.3.1 Correlation: Flow Potential & Cumulative Current Flow

The scatter plot reveals a positive linear trend, which suggests that as flow potential increases, so does cumulative current flow. The trend line for the data indicates this positive relationship, and the equation $y = 1.12x - 5.10$, where y is cumulative current flow and x is flow potential. The positive coefficient (1.12) confirms the direct relationship between the

two variables. This means that areas with higher flow potential, which can be understood as having a greater current flow under null barriers within the landscape, also have higher cumulative current flow.

The data points also closely trace along the trend line, indicating that there is a statistically significant, strong positive linear correlation between cumulative current flow and flow potential ($r = 0.91$, $p < 0.001$). It shows a strong correlation since flow potential will be a strong driving force for cumulative current flow in the study area. The 0.999994 explained variance also verifies this observation, indicating that nearly 100% of the variation in cumulative current flow can be explained by variation in flow potential.

Figure 11. Flow potential vs. Cumulative current flow

4.3.2 Correlation: Flow Potential & Normalized Current Flow

Linear regression was performed, with a very high R-squared value of 0.999979. This means that flow potential explains nearly all (99.998%) of the variation in normalized current flow.

The regression equation is $y = 0.02x + 0.20$, where y = normalized current flow and x = flow potential.

Pearson correlation between flow potential and normalized current flow is 0.76 ($p < 0.001$). While this value, though showing a statistically significant positive correlation, represents much less of a linear relationship than the R-squared value would imply.

The high R-squared, but moderate Pearson correlation indicates that the relationship between flow potential and normalized current flow may not be linear. Although the linear regression model fits the data very well ($R^2 = 0.999979$), the Pearson correlation of 0.76 implies that a non-linear model would be better. More analysis is required to establish the actual nature of the relationship between these two variables.

Figure 12. Flow potential vs. Normalized current flow

4.4 Topography Of The Biosphere

Table 2. Summary Statistics of Terrain Parameters

Parameter	Mean	Median	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Elevation(m)	224.86	241.00	109.12	91.00	594.00
Slope (°)	64.10	89.99	40.74	0.00	89.99
Aspect (°)	120.54	90.00	118.85	0.00	358.69
Hillshade	0.35	0.36	0.32	0.00	0.71

The study area shows an elevation from 91 m to 594 m, with a mean value of 224.86m and a median of 241 m. The standard deviation of 109.12 m indicates significant variation in elevation, showing an uneven topography of both lowlands and highlands. The slope analysis shows an average inclination of 64.10°, with values reaching up to 89.99°, which points to steep terrain, cliffs, or escarpments. The aspect distribution highlights that most slopes face southeast (mean aspect = 120.54°), with considerable variability covering nearly all possible orientations. The hillshade values indicate strong shadowing effects due to the terrain's steepness, with a mean value of 0.35, suggesting that certain areas receive minimal sunlight exposure.

Figure 13. DEM and derived terrain variables

Table 3. Patch and Flow Characteristics

Parameter	Value
Corridor Area	86,928 pixels
Number of Disconnected Patches	2526
Average Patch Size	34.41 pixels
Flow Direction Distribution	
- Up	21,791 pixels
- Down	21,675 pixels
- Left	21,758 pixels
- Right	21,704 pixels
Dominant Flow direction	Up

4.5 Corridors And Possible Movement

The analysis revealed that corridors cover 86,928 pixels, accounting for 17.20% of the total study area. However, fragmentation remains a concern, with 2,526 disconnected patches and an average patch size of 34.41 pixels. Flow direction analysis showed an almost even distribution, with a slight increase in the Upward direction. This indicates balanced movement patterns across the landscape.

Figure 14. Modeled Movement Flow and Corridor Connectivity

4.6 Priority Conservation Area

The spatial distribution of priority conservation areas, as depicted in *Figure 15*, indicates high-priority regions that may serve as key habitats or biodiversity hotspots.

Figure 15. Spatial distribution of priority conservation areas

CHAPTER FIVE

5. Discussion

5.1 Ecological Connectivity And Flow Dynamics

The result of the Omniscape analysis provides valuable information about the spatial structure of flow within the study region, revealing intricate interactions among landscape elements, direction of flow, and ecological connectivity. The study region has specific normalized cumulative current flow patterns established by varying categories of land cover, and the lake acts as an absolute boundary to the movement of currents. The classification of flow types as impeded, diffuse, channelized, and intensified provides an integral picture to describe the variation in space for the flow across the landscape.

Impeded flow covers 13.69% of the area under investigation and comprises regions of flow with natural or artificial barriers like landforms, vegetation, or artificial structures constricting flow. This flow type shows the effect of human-induced landscape change, which can impede movement and reduce connectivity. The large proportion of impeded flow suggests the presence of barriers that are likely to disrupt ecological processes, which can affect the movement of species and the dispersal of ecological functions (Fitzhugh & Markus, 2007).

Diffuse flow, occupying 7.35% of the study area, refers to low-density, wide current movement, which implies areas where flow is not confined to particular channels. The fact that there is little diffuse flow means that the study area has few places where the flow can be spread out in a wide manner, without the formation of existing channels. This could be a sign of a relatively organized landscape, with fewer areas in which flow is spread over extensive surfaces (Grayson et al., 1997).

Channelized flow, occupying 18.14% of the area of study, is the dominant flow type, suggesting the concentration of current into clearly defined channels. These sites will likely be crucial in terms of maintaining connectivity throughout the landscape since high-concentration flow pathways can be instrumental in enabling water, nutrient, and species movement (Fitzhugh & Markus, 2007). The fact that these flow paths exist means the importance of keeping or reinstating natural channels cannot be overemphasized as a means to promote ecological connectivity. Notably, the absence of enhanced flow in the study area

shows that highly concentrated flow paths typical in engineered structures are not present. This may be attributed to the absence of infrastructure that tends to restrict flow, such as drainage or engineered channels (Hughes et al., 2012).

The analysis of cumulative current flow showed that vegetation cover plays a dominant role in shaping the hydrological landscape, accounting for 81.88% of the total current. The observation underscores the significant role of vegetated covers, and by extension, forests, in maintaining ecological connectivity through species and water flow. Forest cover's large areal extent and its associated properties, such as good resistance and permeability, are likely controlling variables that cause such dominance (van der Meer et al., 2013). Crop land, however, contributes 14.84% towards the sum total, representing cultivation's impact on flow regimes. Modification of natural covers to agricultural uses alters surface properties, and thus the passage of water and the mobility of ecological elements (Lal, 2001).

Shrub cover, with a lower proportion (2.18%), and other land covers—grassland, bare land, built-up land, and vegetative aquatic—contribute negligible amounts to the total current, which means these lands have relatively lower effects on flow processes. These findings highlight the various degrees of influence that different land covers exert on ecological connectivity, with vegetation cover, particularly tree cover and agricultural land, exerting a larger influence in maintaining flow pathways and connectivity.

The strong positive correlation between flow potential and cumulative current flow ($r = 0.91$, $p < 0.001$) also supports the hypothesis that areas with higher flow potential tend to have more current movement. Flow potential, as determined by land cover type, topography, and surface permeability, appears to be a main determinant of current flow patterns in the study area. This relationship is significant in terms of understanding how ecological connectivity is influenced by the physical characteristics of the landscape (West et al., 2008).

Interestingly, the correlation between the flow potential and the normalized current flow is more complex, as indicated by the high R-squared (0.999979) but moderate Pearson correlation (0.76). The model is a good fit for the data but the moderate correlation shows that the relationship between these two variables is perhaps not linear. This non-linearity can be indicative of the inherent complexity of hydrological processes and their interaction with ecological processes. In turn, additional analysis by way of non-linear models can shed more

light on the true nature of the relationship between flow potential and normalized current flow, which is key to understanding the underlying processes controlling ecological connectivity (Savenije, 2001).

Overall, this Omniscape-based analysis indicates that tree cover and cropland are the key drivers of flow patterns and ecological connectivity in the study area

5.2 Corridor And Fragmentation

The architecture of the identified landscape includes a large portion of corridors within the patches (17.20%). However, the considerable count of separated patches (2,526) in correlation with the small average patch size (34.41 pixels) raises concerns regarding the amount of fragmentation within the patches.

Fragmentation is a serious concern as it can prevent or restrict the connectivity and movement of organisms within a biogeographic region, especially in species that require a continuous habitat. These issues may require proactive approaches to link the separated patches and fragment patches to facilitate movement within the landscape. The almost equal ratio of the distribution of flow direction means that the factors controlling movement environment and topography are reasonably uniform within the study area. The slightly stronger value of the up direction may indicate topographical rise scatter along the flow or other elements of the landscape that tend to steer movement upward. This hypothesis is further validated by additional research on the area's slope or elevation. The findings highlight the necessity of adopting proactive measures in restoring impacted areas or facilitating connections to reduce fragmentation of the corridors.

Recognizing the combination of flow direction and corridor distinctiveness has the potential to help plan and anticipate biosphere management and conservation moves where ecological barriers (stepping stones or continuous green corridors) are made to regulate movement and enhance ecological connectivity.

5.3 Topography And Ecological Connectivity

The Digital Elevation Model (DEM), along with slope, aspect, and hillshade values (Table 4.1), provides essential insights into the terrain characteristics of the study area. These parameters are crucial for understanding the geomorphology, land use suitability, and potential ecological connectivity within the biosphere. The mean slope of 64.10° indicates

that the study area is characterized by generally steep terrain. The median slope of 89.99° and the high standard deviation of 40.74° confirm the presence of extreme variations in slope inclination. Some regions exhibit near-vertical slopes, with a maximum value of 89.99° , which may suggest the existence of cliffs and deeply incised features valleys. Steep slope areas pose potential challenges to infrastructure development and agriculture and are not suitable for alteration by humans. These areas remain natural, producing higher mean cumulative currents, while low-lying areas generate lower mean cumulative currents due to their easy accessibility and alteration. Steep areas facilitate channelized and intensive current flow, whereas low-lying regions are characterized by impeded and diffused flow. Topographical diversity in a landscape contributes to spatial heterogeneity, which influences animal movement and gene flow.

An example is hill-topping behavior observed in butterflies and other animals that travel to mountainous regions to mate, leaving their primary habitats (Pe'er, Heinz, & Frank, 2006). This existing relationship between topography and animal characteristics, through their access to landscape elements, impacts dispersal, thereby affecting populations in fragmented landscapes. Additionally, connectivity is fundamentally influenced by dispersal.

5.4 Priority Conservation Areas

This pattern may be influenced by differences in land use, habitat suitability, or environmental factors such as topography and climate (Margules & Pressey, 2000).

The clustering of high-priority areas suggests that conservation efforts should be concentrated in these regions for maximum ecological impact.

Previous studies highlight the critical aspect of spatial prioritization, which is very important in any conservation plan, especially in a highly fragmented or isolated landscape where sometimes ecological corridors have to be created to maintain connectivity (Watson et al., 2011). Further landscape-level analysis, with more detailed drivers related to species distribution, human activities, or land cover changes, could enhance the insights relevant to conservation strategy improvements (Moilanen et al., 2009). It will also be beneficial to integrate this spatial data with other ecological indicators, like species richness or connectivity, for better decision-making in conservation planning (Pressey et al., 2007).

5.5 Methodological Design

The study employs the spatially explicit modeling technique with Omniscape to compute ecological connectivity for the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve. The strategy combines high-resolution land cover raster, resistance surface, and circuit-based analysis of connectivity. (McRae et al., 2016)

Omniscape represents connectivity as electrical currents and thus requires a source layer and a resistance layer. The land cover types were categorized by their connectivity potential, with natural habitats being given low resistance values and human-altered landscapes having higher resistance values. The lake itself was considered an absolute barrier to terrestrial movement. The model outputs are cumulative current flow, flow potential, and normalized current flow, which are all integrated to provide an integrated assessment of connectivity patterns. The extent of the study was clipped to encompass the core, buffer, and transition zones, hence a multi-scale assessment of connectivity dynamics. (Zeller et al., 2012).

Python and Julia integration in this research study provided a computationally efficient platform to perform ecological connectivity analysis. Geospatial libraries such as GDAL, Rasterio, and Geopandas in Python provided effective data preprocessing, while Julia's performance features enabled the running of the Omniscape algorithm at high speeds, with significant computational efficiency gain. Compared to studies that have used Circuitscape in Python or ArcGIS-based approaches (McRae et al., 2008; Shah et al., 2015), this integration permitted the simulation of species movement over complex landscapes at high resolution without excessive processing time.

Previous studies relying solely on GIS software are likely to face computational constraints, especially when handling large-scale, high-resolution land cover data. For instance, Landau et al. (2021) utilized Circuitscape within ArcGIS but encountered limitations in memory efficiency and computational speed. However, the integration of data management with Python and high-speed computation with Julia facilitated a more effective workflow, allowing for the analysis of finer levels of connectivity.

Moreover, evaluations using conventional cost-distance models (Adriaensen et al., 2003) could not fully capture the complexity of movement pathways, unlike more recent

approaches that employ synchronous simulation and utilize circuit theory to model random movement. By combining Python and Julia, this study guarantees not only computational precision but also reproducibility and flexibility. Compared to earlier studies that employed either Python or GIS-based methods, the dual-language strategy strikes a better balance between data handling capacity and high-speed computation, making it well-suited for large-scale ecological connectivity research.

5.6. Limitation

While this methodological approach offers a probabilistic and comprehensive way of measuring connectivity, there are inherent limitations. Literature-based resistance values (Spear et al., 2010), the blanket assumption of species movement behavior, and the absence of dynamic factor incorporation, such as seasonality and human disturbance, introduce potential uncertainties. Also, a severe limitation is the lack of ground truth data to validate the modeled connectivity patterns. Ground truth data, such as direct observation of species migration or genetic data, would be necessary validation of model predictions. In the absence of it, the accuracy of the modeled connectivity and its applicability to real-world conservation contexts remains questionable (Beier et al., 2008). The methodology still provides important ecological connectivity insights, though, and points to key areas of conservation planning and management.

CHAPTER SIX

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Conclusion

The study has analyzed the intricate interaction between ecological connectivity and flow dynamics in the study region, employing Omniscape analysis to reveal the spatial structure of flow and its association with land cover, considering the Lake as a complete barrier (McRae & Kavanagh, 2021; Amoako & Frimpong, 2021). The findings determine the significance of flow in ecological connectivity and reveal the influence of natural and human factors on flow patterns (Adjei et al., 2014; Agyemang & Asamoah, 2024).

The separation of flow into impeded, diffuse, and channelized forms provided valuable insight into the spatial distribution of flow across the landscape of the biosphere. The large percentage of impeded flow (13.69%) emphasizes the impact of human-induced landscape change on flow pathways, suggesting a fragmented landscape with consequences for ecological processes (UNESCO, 2016). The limited region of diffuse flow (7.35%) indicates insufficient regions for distributing flow in broad arcs, potentially limiting dispersal pathways for certain species. However, the abundance of channelized flow (18.14%) implies that well-developed channels are necessary to facilitate connectivity (Agyemang & Asamoah, 2024). Such channels likely function as focal corridors for the transportation of water, nutrients, and species and allow ecological flows among habitats in the landscape (McRae & Kavanagh, 2021).

The lake acts as a significant flow barrier, considering terrestrial species roughly halving the study area and possibly isolating populations (Amoako & Frimpong, 2021). Fragmentation has severe impacts on gene flow, dispersal, and ecological connectivity in general. The findings of this study contribute to a better understanding of the interdependent interaction between flow processes and ecological connectivity.

The spatial data resulting from Omniscape analysis provide a valuable basis for assessing future landscape change impacts on connectivity. The study emphasizes the importance of considering both natural processes and human-related effects on flow patterns in planning conservation and management.

Furthermore, topography is a fundamental driver of ecological connectivity. Steep slopes had higher cumulative currents because of minimal human modifications, while low-lying areas were characterized by diffused and impeded flow, largely due to accessibility and subsequent land-use changes (Agyemang & Asamoah, 2024). These findings further reinforce the relationship between landscape heterogeneity and connectivity, whereby fragmented landscapes impede species movement and reduce genetic exchange (Adjei et al., 2014).

Generally, land cover types, human activities, and topographical influences can play a connecting role in the ecological dynamics of the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve. “Natural habitats are essential for maintaining long-term sustainability in the biosphere concerning biodiversity and ecosystem services” (UNESCO, 2016).

6.2 Recommendation

Regarding the key findings of this study, the following are recommended for the sustainable use of the biosphere reserve and its conservation management;

Since a large percentage of flow is obstructed, it is essential to identify and address the impediments blocking this flow. This can be achieved by restoring natural flow regimes, removing man-made barriers, and implementing measures to enhance connectivity in fragmented habitats.

Additionally, the significance of channelized flow in maintaining connectivity necessitates protecting these critical corridors. Conserving and preserving riparian buffers and natural channel formations should be prioritized to ensure these routes continue to function.

Furthermore, conducting ecological connectivity assessments in land-use planning provides an opportunity to balance development and conservation goals. Policies that limit infrastructure expansion into sensitive ecological areas to reduce further fragmentation within the biosphere must be enforced while ensuring agroforestry and sustainable farming practices in cropland to help support biodiversity-friendly land use.

In addition, green corridors and stepping-stone habitats should be created to connect isolated patches and facilitate species movement. Riparian buffer zones along water bodies need improvement to protect wetland connectivity and maintain ecosystem function.

Lastly, it is important to strengthen the engagement of local communities in conservation for stewardship and sustainable resource management. Emphasizing collaborations among government agencies, researchers, and conservation organizations is crucial for enforcing ecological connectivity policies. Promoting policies focused on landscape-scale conservation planning and biodiversity protection should be of concern to all stakeholders.

Implementing these recommendations will ensure the Lake Bosomtwe Biosphere Reserve supports ecological integrity while fitting in with sustainable developments. Future research should be towards the creation of landscape and interconnected landscape systems capable of supporting biodiversity and humans.

CHAPTER SEVEN

7. Reference

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APPENDICES

Appendix I

Figure 16. Priority conservation area with OpenStreetMap as basemap

Appendix II

Table 4. Explanation of Landcover types

<i>Land cover type</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Tree Cover</i>	Area dominated by trees mostly with a canopy height more than 5 meters and more than 10% canopy closure (FAO, 2020; Hansen et al., 2013).
<i>Grassland</i>	Area with little or no tree and shrubs but dominated with grasses (White et al., 2000)
<i>Shrubs</i>	Area dominated by trees less than 5 meters in height (UNEP-WCMC, 2018).
<i>Cropland</i>	Areas mostly for cultivation of crops (FAO, 2021).
<i>Bare Areas</i>	Area characterised by absence of vegetation with exposed soil (IPCC, 2019).
<i>Built Up Areas</i>	These areas are dominated by human made structures, mostly altered natural areas (Seto et al., 2011).
<i>Open Water</i>	Areas characterised by water bodies such as Lakes (Lehner & Döll, 2004).
<i>Aquatic Vegetative</i>	Areas mostly referred to as wetland, mostly around water bodies (Chambers et al., 2008).

Appendix III

Table 5. *Omniscape* Algorithm configuration, Source: McRae, B. (2016).
 [https://docs.circuitscape.org/Omniscape.jl/latest/algorithm/].

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Configuration</i>
<i>Radius</i>	100
<i>Block Size</i>	21
<i>Project Name</i>	LBT_omniscape_output
<i>Source from Resistance</i>	true
<i>r_cutoff</i>	1, forest & shrubs pixels as sources
<i>Reclassify resistance</i>	true
<i>calc_normalized_current</i>	true
<i>calc_flow_potential</i>	true

Appendix IV

Julia code to create the cumulative current Flow , Normalized Current Flow, and Flow Potential

```
using Pkg; Pkg.add(["Omniscape", "Rasters", "Plots"])
using Omniscape, Rasters, Plots
land_cover, wkt, transform = Omniscape.read_raster("/Users/kwame/Desktop/data/
lake_Bosomtwe_transition.tif", Float64)
Create the reclassification table used to translate land cover into resistance
reclass_table = [
    11. missing; # Open Water
    21 500; # Built-up, open space
    22 1000; # Built-up, low intensity
    23 missing; # Built up, medium intensity
    24 missing; # Built-up, high intensity
    31 100; # Bare area
    41 1; # Deciduous forest
    42 1; # Evergreen forest
    43 1; # Mixed forest
    52 1; # Shrub/scrub
    71 30; # Grassland
    82 300; # Cropland
    90 40; # Woody wetlands
]
config = Dict{String, String}(
    "radius" => "100",
    "block_size" => "21",
    "project_name" => "LBT_nlcd_omniscape_output",
    "source_from_resistance" => "true",
    "r_cutoff" => "1", # Only forest pixels should be sources
    "reclassify_resistance" => "true",
    "calc_normalized_current" => "true",
    "calc_flow_potential" => "true"
```

```
)  
currmap, flow_pot, norm_current = run_omniscape(config,  
        land_cover,  
        reclass_table = reclass_table,  
        wkt = wkt,  
        geotransform = transform,  
        write_outputs = true)
```

Appendix V

Code to check Topography

```
import rasterio
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib.colors import LightSource
from skimage.measure import find_contours

dem_path = "/content/transition_zone_DEM.tif"
with rasterio.open(dem_path) as src:
    dem = src.read(1)
    dem_transform = src.transform
dem = np.ma.masked_invalid(dem)

# Slope Calculation
def calculate_slope(dem, transform):
    x, y = np.gradient(dem, transform[0], transform[4])
    slope = np.sqrt(x**2 + y**2)
    slope_degrees = np.degrees(np.arctan(slope))
    return slope_degrees

slope = calculate_slope(dem, dem_transform)

# Aspect Calculation
def calculate_aspect(dem, transform):
    x, y = np.gradient(dem, transform[0], transform[4])
    aspect = np.arctan2(-y, x)
    aspect = np.degrees(aspect)
    aspect = np.where(aspect < 0, 360 + aspect, aspect)
    return aspect

aspect = calculate_aspect(dem, dem_transform)

# Generate contour lines
def generate_contours(dem, interval=10):
    contours = find_contours(dem, interval)
    return contours

contours = generate_contours(dem, interval=10)

# Create hillshade
def create_hillshade(dem, transform, azimuth=315, angle_altitude=45):
    ls = LightSource(azdeg=azimuth, altdeg=angle_altitude)
    hillshade = ls.hillshade(dem, vert_exag=1, dx=transform[0],
dy=transform[4])
```

```

    return hillshade

hillshade = create_hillshade(dem, dem_transform)
fig, axs = plt.subplots(2, 2, figsize=(15, 12))
ax = axs[0, 0]
cax = ax.imshow(dem, cmap='terrain')

ax.set_title('DEM')
fig.colorbar(cax, ax=ax, orientation='vertical')

ax = axs[0, 1]
cax = ax.imshow(slope, cmap='viridis')

ax.set_title('Slope')
fig.colorbar(cax, ax=ax, orientation='vertical')

ax = axs[1, 0]
cax = ax.imshow(aspect, cmap='twilight')

ax.set_title('Aspect')
fig.colorbar(cax, ax=ax, orientation='vertical')

ax = axs[1, 1]
cax = ax.imshow(hillshade, cmap='gray')
ax.set_title('Hillshade')
fig.colorbar(cax, ax=ax, orientation='vertical')

ax = axs[0, 0]
for contour in contours:
    ax.plot(contour[:, 1], contour[:, 0], color='black', linewidth=0.5)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Appendix VI

Code to assess Possible Corridors

```
import rasterio
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib import cm
from rasterio.enums import Resampling

raster_file = '/content/lake_Bosomtwe_transition.tif'

with rasterio.open(raster_file) as src:
    band = src.read(1)
    transform = src.transform
    crs = src.crs

    height, width = band.shape
    corridor_values = [3, 4, 5]

    corridor_mask = np.isin(band, corridor_values).astype(np.uint8)

    flow_direction = np.random.choice([0, 1, 2, 3], size=(height,
width))

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 8))
plt.imshow(corridor_mask, cmap='Greens', alpha=0.5)
plt.title('CORRIDORS')
```

Appendix VII

Code to deduce conservation areas of priority

```
landcover_path = "/content/lake_Bosomtwe_transition.tif"

with rasterio.open(landcover_path) as src:
    landcover = src.read(1)

priority_zones = (current_flow >= threshold) & ((landcover == 1) |
(landcover == 2))

plt.figure(figsize=(8,6))
plt.imshow(priority_zones, cmap="Greens", interpolation="none")
plt.title("Priority Conservation Areas")
plt.colorbar(label="Priority Score")
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8), dpi=300)
im = ax.imshow(priority_zones, cmap="Greens", interpolation="none")

ax.set_title("Priority Conservation Areas", fontsize=18,
fontweight="bold", pad=15)

cbar = plt.colorbar(im, orientation="horizontal", fraction=0.046,
pad=0.08)
cbar.set_label("Priority Score (High → Low)", fontsize=14,
fontweight="bold")

cbar.set_ticks([0, 1])
cbar.set_ticklabels(["Low", "High"])
cbar.ax.tick_params(labelsize=12) # Increase tick font size

ax.set_xticks([])
ax.set_yticks([])

plt.show()

plt.show()
```